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PEDAGOGICAL SITUATION OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING

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Abstract: The article addresses the issue of teaching critical thinking in the context of English learning. Critical thinking is a fundamental principle of successful professional activity. The educational process in Uzbekistan, which has long been hampered by repetitive procedures, outdated material, and antiquated techniques, is currently undergoing a series of adjustments to align with European Bologna Process norms.

Key words: critical thinking, pedagogy, video materials, technology, student, curriculum, process, education, teaching.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada ingliz tilini o'rganish kontekstida tanqidiy fikrlashni o'rgatish masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Tanqidiy fikrlash – muvaffaqiyatli professional faoliyatning asosiy tamoyilidir. Uzoq vaqtdan beri takrorlanuvchi tartiblar, eskirgan materiallar va uslublar tufayli to'siqlarga uchragan O'zbekistondagi ta'lim jarayoni bugungi kunda Yevropa Boloniya jarayoni me'yorlariga moslashtirish maqsadida qator tuzatishlardan o'tmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: tanqidiy fikrlash, pedagogika, video materiallar, texnologiya, talaba, o'quv dasturi, jarayon, ta'lim, o'qitish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается проблема обучения критическому мышлению в контексте изучения английского языка. Критическое мышление является основополагающим принципом успешной профессиональной деятельности. Образовательный процесс в Узбекистане, который долгое время тормозился повторяющимися процедурами, устаревшими материалами и методиками, в настоящее время претерпевает ряд корректировок для приведения в соответствие с европейскими нормами Болонского процесса.

Ключевые слова: критическое мышление, педагогика, видеоматериалы, технология, студент, учебная программа, процесс, образование, преподавание.

INTRODUCTION

Many scientists and philologists have conducted research on the use of video resources in education. Many teachers agree that using voice, text, and graphics to teach English has proven to be beneficial. As a result, video materials provide both practical and theoretical information; they also serve as sources of inspiration and can be utilized to create interdisciplinary connections. According to research, students who frequently complete assignments based on video materials improve more rapidly and acquire not only language skills such as listening and speaking, but also critical thinking abilities. Activities aimed at developing critical thinking can be linked to teaching academic writing and speaking, particularly presentations and discussions. Developing an effective system for organizing and storing video resources can enhance students' critical thinking skills and increase instructional effectiveness.

The educational process currently taking place in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan is undergoing a series of essential and drastic changes. The focus is increasingly shifting towards the type of personality the educational institution should develop, rather than the traditional goal of producing a specialist in a specific field. However, the Uzbek educational system still contains many outdated laws and regulations that hinder the modern trajectory of youth education. Therefore, teachers should strive to provide the highest possible quality of instruction despite these systemic flaws. One of the key aspects of educating a person is teaching them how to think critically. There are various methods for achieving this goal, including reading and debating literature, writing essays, role-playing, and conducting case studies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

John Dewey, a renowned researcher, emphasized the importance of incorporating critical thinking skills into the curriculum to benefit both the community and society as a whole. R. J. Sternberg's work on critical thinking offers a comprehensive perspective. Several other scholars, including R. T. Pithers, R. Soden, and P. A. Facione, have also advocated for the essential role of critical thinking in education and professional development. While scientific studies are valuable, they often overlook the potential of using audiovisual resources to enhance critical thinking skills.

Previous research on the use of video in education is diverse, exploring its impact across different age groups, motivational aspects, and memory-enhancing processes. Dr. Thomas J. Garza is one of the most prominent and practical researchers in this area, focusing on the application of video materials in advanced foreign language instruction. Other scholars such as C. Chen, M. Lemmens, and K. A. Linsenmeier have examined the role of videos as tools for discussion and professional development, benefiting both students and educators ^[4].

Although the term “critical thinking” may sound overly serious, it is an essential life skill. Historically, the roots of this intellectual practice can be traced back to thinkers like Socrates, Aristotle, Plato, and Heraclitus—often considered the founding fathers of rational inquiry. However, in many post-Soviet countries, fostering this innate capability remains a challenge. Education systems often train students to follow instructions blindly, fulfilling tasks strictly as outlined by supervisors and the curriculum. Teachers are rarely encouraged to provide constructive criticism or engage in evaluative thinking. As a result, educational practices tend to prioritize surface-level compliance rather than deeper intellectual engagement. In the digital age—where information on topics like astrophysics and artificial intelligence is readily available through the internet and academic libraries—education must shift its focus. The ability to process information, evaluate evidence, draw reasoned conclusions, and generate new ideas should be central to modern learning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

All people are capable of critical thinking and, to a greater or lesser extent, are able to make reasonable judgments based on thoughtful evaluation. From a young age, everyone is a scientist, learning about the world. However, the ability to think critically can be significantly affected by the society in which a person is raised—particularly by the level of superstition and misinformation (often consisting of far-fetched ideas) prevalent in that society.

To think well, a person must be self-disciplined and willing to question fundamental goals and ideals, even those passed down by parents or considered sacred. This aspect of critical thinking leads to several essential traits that a person must possess or develop in order to think critically. Here it is appropriate to quote from a research paper by Lai E.R. ^[5, p. 10–11]:

“The most commonly cited critical thinking dispositions include:

- Open-mindedness;
- Fair-mindedness;
- The propensity to seek reason;
- Inquisitiveness;
- The desire to be well-informed;
- Flexibility and respect for, and willingness to entertain, others' viewpoints.”

In addition to the above-mentioned dispositions, we would like to propose a few more. The first is honesty. Critical thinking does not tolerate lies or self-deception. One must be able to admit what they know, what they do not know, and how much of their desire actually influences the reality around them.

No conclusion can be considered reasonable if it is based on wishful thinking—beliefs rooted in desire rather than reality. The term wishful thinking aptly describes reasoning filled with self-deception. A thinker should seek answers to the question “What is it?” rather than “What do I want it to appear to be?” Otherwise, such thinking becomes nothing more than daydreaming.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Critical thinking does not recognize authority. No assertion can be considered true solely on the grounds that it was said by an individual with a certain status. Authority often plays on our biological features that are generally useful—among the children of our wild ancestors, those who listened to parental warnings and

believed them in the absence of personal experience often survived. This mechanism was successfully transmitted to us. In the unconscious phase of growing up, we tend to believe everything elders say, and although the power of faith weakens with age, an authoritative figure can grow stronger and compensate for this gap. Teachers, governors, powerful individuals, celebrities, religious representatives, and even persuasive liars can successfully perform the role of the “knowledgeable” authority—those assumed to possess more knowledge and experience.

However, critical thinking does not tolerate authority—it requires evidence that is independent of the individual’s personality. The other two vital components of critical thinking are motivation and creativity. Problem-solving and decision-making should be activities that a person feels naturally inclined to and eager to fulfill. Personal characteristics such as persistence and diligence play a significant role in the thinking process. A person who is lazy or always ready to give up will never succeed in critical thinking, as it is always a challenging path to formulate ideas or summarize content meaningfully. Without creative thinking, a person may only be able to criticize and object, lacking the imagination to produce new arguments or identify areas of disagreement. When a person is motivated and interested in the subject, they start to “twirl” it from different angles, using creative thinking to produce new, unknown variants and conclusions. It is important to note that teaching critical thinking should never be conducted under pressure or by a teacher with a domineering character. Freedom of thought is at the core of this approach to learning. Students should be encouraged to express their opinions—but never forced to. One of the problems in the modern educational system of Uzbekistan is the partial neglect of motivation. Curricula often include themes that do not address up-to-date issues or rely on outdated methods and techniques. Nevertheless, students are required to memorize this content by heart—even when they know such knowledge will never be applied in their professional field.

Video materials as an instrument for the development of critical thinking. When discussing the use of video in the educational process, it must be emphasized that video materials are an almost perfect resource for teaching. However, the materials used in education must strictly meet specific requirements. Videos should be highly informative, have high-quality visuals, clear audio, and a logical plot. Ideally, the video should include subtitles, and it should not be too long or too flashy. These recommendations are applicable across all disciplines, but we should focus especially on teaching critical thinking in English language classes, because English, being a language of global communication, touches on all spheres of life. While learning a language, people learn to express themselves—to think and communicate, to tackle problems and analyze situations, to make plans, and to argue or debate various topics. Therefore, English language learning activates more cognitive operations than performing mathematical equations, solving physics problems, or calculating chemical ratios. University-level English includes both professional topics and general knowledge. Using video materials offers numerous advantages: visibility, informativeness, and entertainment value are the most significant. Students in groups where topics are taught using video materials show better motivation and a deeper understanding of the topic. As this issue is of great importance, there are specific requirements that can enhance productivity and improve the educational process.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, we may conclude that the introduction of video materials into the educational process increases the effectiveness of teaching critical thinking skills—specifically, helping students apply these skills to the tasks and themes they are assigned. Since the video resources are freely accessible and cover all necessary topics, we believe they can be effectively used across various disciplines.

It is frequently challenging to comprehend the narrator or characters in the videos, as most of them are in English, particularly scientific English. However, as previously mentioned, the visual demonstrability of these materials is a significant advantage. It serves as a motivator for students and fosters the creation of diverse assignments and discussions around academic challenges.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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